

OBTAINING METHYLCELLULOSE HYDROGELS CONTAINING SILVER NANOPARTICLES AND STUDYING ITS PROPERTIES

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Abstract: In this work, we present in situ preparation of silver nanoparticles by reduction of silver nitrate by methylcellulose. The aim of this study was to prepare a stable solution of methylcellulose-silver, convert it to solid film, redissolve it and determine how this process influences the form and properties of the prepared NPs.

Keywords: silver nanoparticles, methylcellulose, film, infection.

Introduction. Chronic wounds represent a severe clinical problem affecting 1–2% of the population in developed countries [1]. Being hard to heal, chronic wounds are challenging both for patients and for healthcare systems, and account for 2–3% of the healthcare budgets. According to clinical literature, chronic wounds can be assigned to three main categories: vascular ulcers, diabetic ulcers, and pressure ulcers. Even if no single, widely accepted definition of chronic wound exists, in most cases, a wound is defined as chronic if it has not healed within a certain amount of time, ranging from 4 to 6 weeks for most authors, or up to 3 months, as noted in standard surgical textbooks [2]. Regardless of the time, chronic wounds share some standard features, e.g., persistent inflammation, recurrent infections with possible formation of antibiotic-resistant biofilms, and deficiency of stem cells. Combined, these pathophysiological phenomena result in the wound's inability to heal.

Infection is a critical complication in chronic wounds, often leading to persistent non-healing, significant morbidity, or even mortality. Alkalinity is associated with infection in chronic wounds, even if its cause is still unclear. Bacteria metabolism could be responsible for the local increase of pH due to the release of ammonia and polyamines, which can impair the oxygenation of wound tissue and promote necrosis [3].

This process is affordable, environmentally friendly and effective method how to prepare materials for various applications, as it does not need any seed, template or surfactant. It is possible to influence the properties of the synthesized nanoparticles (NPs) depending on the conditions during preparation. The colloid solutions of nanoparticles can be easily converted into solid films in order to prevent aggregation of the prepared NPs. Modifying the preparation conditions of the films or incorporating additives enables control of material properties of the prepared films. One of the perspective polysaccharides is methylcellulose (MC), which is very attractive because of its solubility in water, surface activity, and thermal gelation ability. [4].

Moreover, cellulose and its derivatives are nontoxic and non-allergenic to humans, therefore they are widely used in food, cosmetic, pharmaceutical, and biomedical applications.

The importance of silver NPs increases due to the increasing emergence of new strains of bacteria resistant to antibiotics. Small silver particles attack the cell walls disrupting vital functions of the cell. They are able to penetrate into the bacteria and interact with sulphur and phosphorus containing biomolecules such as DNA. Furthermore, Ag⁺ ions get released from the NPs and disturb the ability of DNA molecules to replicate as they become condensed. Silver ions interact with thiol groups in proteins, which induces inactivation of the bacterial proteins.

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) embedded in MC matrix can broaden utility of this natural polysaccharide. The most valuable advantage these materials poses is their antibacterial activity against a wide spectrum of bacteria and molds such properties are highly demanded in medicine and food packaging.

The aim of this study was to prepare a stable solution of MC-Ag, convert it to solid film, redissolve it and determine how this process influences the form and properties of the prepared NPs. MC was analysed by UV-vis spectrometry.

Fig. 1. Structural formula of methylcellulose

As shown in Figure 1, the molecular formula of methylcellulose is presented, which is mainly formed by the exchange of an H atom in groups 2, 4 or 6 with a CH₃ group. For the formation of AgNPs, a 1% aqueous solution of MC was heated for 60 minutes at 80°C to obtain a homogeneous suspension then the removed of the gel fraction by centrifugation (CenLee 20K, China) at a speed of 10000 rpm for 15 minutes. Calculated quantities of 0.1-

0.001 mol/l aqueous solutions of AgNO₃ were added dropwise to the MC solution under stirring until a homogeneous solution was obtained.

The photochemical reduction of Ag⁺ immobilized in the MC was performed at different times at a temperature of 25°C by irradiation with a DRSh-250 high-pressure mercury vapor lamp with wattage 35 watts and wavelength $\lambda = 365$ nm. The dispersions of AgNPs in the matrix of MC hydrogels were prepared by ultrasonic treatment with the help of UZDN-1 and U-4.2 ultrasonic dispersers. AgNPs containing MC films were obtained by the casting of preformed hydrogel on the degreased glass plate followed by drying in air at a temperature range of 25-40°C.

Numerous studies have shown that polymers-containing AgNPs based biomaterials possess good antimicrobial and wound-healing properties. Therefore, we have studied the conditions of obtaining Ag⁺MC hydrogels containing stabilized AgNPs by using photochemical methods [7]. A comparison of different methods of silver ions reduction to nanometallic state has shown that photochemical reduction is the most effective to control the size of NPs and obtain products pure of the reducing agent transformation products [34].

Investigation, the formation of AgNPs in 0.2-0.4 wt.% solutions of MC with DS of 0.78 and DP of 500 was carried out by photochemical reduction of Ag⁺ [7].

For the photochemical generation of AgNPs in the MC solution, one can suppose that the reaction sequence according to the Mott-Gurney mechanism.

The methylcellulose films were stored for several weeks at room temperature and then re-dissolved in distilled water. A comparison of UV-vis spectra shows that when films obtained from photochemically reduced solutions for different times were re-thaw and analyzed, 30 minutes in photochemically reduced solution was found to be optimal.

It was found that silver nanoparticles can be prepared *in situ* in the MC matrix. The higher temperature during preparation was more effective in obtaining a good solution than the laboratory temperature. Optimal times of photochemical reduction of MC solution containing silver cations were determined.

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